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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN ORAL HEALTH AND DIABETES IN
PAKISTANI POPULATION**Dr Rabia Javed¹, Dr Bazgha Muneer², Dr Iram Akbar Khan¹¹Rawalpindi Medical University**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Oral conditions are known to affect almost half of the world's population. Dental decay alone affects nearly 2.5 billion people, making it the most prevalent condition worldwide.

Objectives: The main objective of the study is to find the association between oral health and diabetes in Pakistani population.

Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University during June 2018 to June 2019. The data was collected from diabetic patients who visited the OPD of the hospital regularly. The data was collected through a self-administered questionnaire to find the oral health of diabetic patients.

Results: The data was collected from 100 patients. The mean age of the participants ranged from 25 to 55 years. The majority were in the age bracket of 25–40 years. More than half the participants (55.2%) were not engaged in employment and 46.1% had no formal qualifications. Over half the participants (52.3%) were from low to middle income families (<\$40 000 and \$40 000 – <\$80 000) and just over a third had health care cards.

Conclusion: It is concluded that outcome of periodontal disease seemed to be influenced by the diabetic state to some degree, but a clear association between diabetes and oral health status was not found.

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral conditions are known to affect almost half of the world's population. Dental decay alone affects nearly 2.5 billion people, making it the most prevalent condition worldwide. More than 7% of the world population suffers from severe chronic periodontitis. More Indians suffer from caries and periodontitis than their South Asian counterparts [1]. A recent survey reports prevalence of caries and periodontitis among rural Indian adults was nearly 65% for both conditions. It has been estimated that the total health loss associated with oral conditions is comparable to that for hypertensive heart disease, schizophrenia, and all maternal conditions combined [2]. Besides, India has the maximum number of adults with diabetes in the South-East Asian Region (72.9 million) with the numbers expected to rise to 134 million in 2045.

A number of oral disorders have been associated with diabetes mellitus. The association of diabetes mellitus and periodontal diseases (such as gingivitis and periodontitis) has received the greatest attention and is the focus of this article [3]. In addition to gingivitis and periodontitis, Ship3 listed dental caries, salivary dysfunction, oral mucosal diseases, oral infections such as candidiasis, taste and other neurosensory disorders. Diabetes mellitus is very prevalent, affecting over 217 million people worldwide, and its prevalence is expected to increase in the future [4]. According to the World Health Organization, at least 366 million people around the world are projected to have diabetes mellitus by the year 2030. Periodontal disease, which is one of the most common dental problems and a major cause of tooth loss, is caused by a variety of oral plaque bacteria. In Japan, approximately 70% of the population aged 15 years or older has some degree of periodontal problems and more than 20% of the population aged 40 years or older have periodontal pockets 4 mm or deeper [5].

Studies establishing the relationship among diabetes mellitus, periodontal health and subsequent tooth loss have been broadly reported. There is ample evidence

of the biological and epidemiological links between periodontal disease and diabetes, especially, type 2 diabetes mellitus. The postulated mechanism for diabetic effects on periodontal disease is that diabetes-enhanced inflammation and apoptosis specifically affect periodontal tissues [6].

Objectives:

The main objective of the study is to find the association between oral health and diabetes in Pakistani population.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Rawalpindi Medical University during June 2018 to June 2019. The data was collected from diabetic patients who visited the OPD of the hospital regularly. The data was collected through a self-administered questionnaire to find the oral health of diabetic patients. The self-administered questionnaire included demographic (i.e., age and gender) and smoking status information (i.e., non-smoker, past-smoker and current-smoker). All dental examinations were performed by dentists from the local dental association, using a dental mirror and a CPI probe. The oral hygiene condition was visually evaluated by examining all teeth present without using disclosing solution as: 1) good, plaque covering less than one-third of tooth surfaces; 2) fair, plaque covering more than one-third but less than two-thirds of tooth surfaces; and, 3) poor, plaque covering more than two-thirds of tooth surfaces.

The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 19. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients. The mean age of the participants ranged from 25 to 55 years. The majority were in the age bracket of 25–40 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographics and obstetric characteristics of participants (n = 100)

Characteristics	Frequency (%)
Age (years)	
25-40	85.9
40-55	11.2
Highest qualification achieved	
No qualifications	46.1
Vocational college	30.7
University	22
Employment status at recruitment	
Working full-time	23.1
Working part-time	17.8
Not working	55.3
Average annual household income	
<\$40 000	20.54
\$40 000 to less than \$80 000	22
\$80 000 to less than \$120 000	23.45
Health Care Card	
Yes	19.5
No	7.3
Private Health Insurance	
Yes	28.9
No	71
Period of diabetes	
1-3 years	2.9
3-5 years	33.4
< 5 years	67.5

More than half the participants (55.2%) were not engaged in employment and 46.1% had no formal qualifications. Over half the participants (52.3%) were from low to middle income families (<\$40 000 and \$40 000 – <\$80 000) and just over a third had health care cards. The most common oral health problems

reported by the 100 participants who gave information were bleedings gums, cavities, sensitivity and 50% reported that dental problems had sometimes or often affected both what they could eat and overall health in general.

Table 2: Perceived oral health status of pregnant women (n = 100)

Variables	Frequency (%)
Oral health status	
Excellent	10.9
Good	29.5
Average	48.2
Fair	7.8
Poor	5.1
Type of oral health problems	
Bleeding gums	60.1
Toothache	16.9
Cavities	3.1
Loose teeth	20.2
Sensitivity	41.6
Teeth that don't look right	15.1
Dental problems affected what to eat and overall health in general	
Never	50.1
Sometimes	41.8
Often	8.8

DISCUSSION:

Even though a clear relationship between diabetes mellitus and periodontal disease was not observed, the outcomes of periodontal disease seemed to be influenced by the diabetic state to some degree [7]. Our hypothesis that the deterioration of periodontal health and subsequent tooth loss leads to a decreased number of posterior occluding tooth pairs was not verified in this research [8]. Because the current results were obtained from a cross-sectional study of a small sample of diabetics, it is difficult to detect significant differences and make causal inferences. In any case, the CPI does not really measure periodontal condition, unlike studies based on the pocket depth or gingival bleeding measurement [9].

Dental professionals should more actively utilize medically and dentally related data in order to investigate the relationship between oral and general health. Doing so will allow more efficient examination of medically and dentally related problems and more readily promote interdisciplinary research [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that outcome of periodontal disease seemed to be influenced by the diabetic state to some degree, but a clear association between diabetes and oral health status was not found. Diabetes mellitus is a disease of which the general public and practicing dentists and dental hygienists should be aware.

REFERENCES:

1. Lalla E, Lamster IB, Feit M, et al. Blockade of RAGE suppresses periodontitis-associated bone loss in diabetic mice. *J Clin Invest* 2000;105(8):1117-1124
2. Ebersole JL, Holt SC, Hansard R, Novak MJ. Microbiologic and immunologic characteristics of periodontal disease in Hispanic Americans with type 2 diabetes. *J Periodontol* 2008;79(4):637-646
3. Molyneaux LM, Constantino MI, McGill M, Zilkens R, Yue DK. Better glycaemic control and risk reduction of diabetic complications in Type 2 diabetes: comparison with the DCCT. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 1998;42(2):77-83
4. Tilg H, Moschen AR. Inflammatory mechanisms in the regulation of insulin resistance. *Mol Med* 2008;14(3-4):222-231.
5. Shultis WA, Weil EJ, Looker HC, et al. Effect of periodontitis on overt nephropathy and end-stage renal disease in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2007;30(2):306-311
6. Chuang SF, Sung JM, Kuo SC, Huanf JJ, Lee SY (2005). Oral and dental manifestations in diabetic and nondiabetic uremic patients receiving hemodialysis. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*, 99(6): 689–695.
7. Mealey BL, Ocampo GL (2007). Diabetes mellitus and periodontal disease. *Periodontol* 2000, 44: 127–153.
8. Namariyama Y (2008). Relationship between community periodontal index and serum antibody levels for periodontopathic microorganisms in a rural population in Kagoshima prefecture. *J Dent Hlth*, 58(1): 44–50.
9. Shinkai R, Hatch J, Sakai S, Mobley CC, Saunders MJ, Rugh JD (2001). Oral function and diet quality in a community-based sample. *J Dent Res*, 80(7): 1625–1630.
10. Ueno M, Yanagisawa T, Shinada K, Ohara S, Kawaguchi Y (2008). Masticatory ability and functional tooth units in Japanese adults. *J Oral Rehabil*, 35(5): 337–344.